

INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE AND TRADITIONAL USES OF MEDICINAL PLANTS IN BANJIR VALLEY, DISTRICT BUNER, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Banjir Valley is located on the Buner–Swat borderline. A total of 68 different plant species were documented for an ethnobotanical study. It was noted that nearly every part of the plants was utilized to prepare remedies of these, leaves of 29 species were used most often, followed by fruits of 16 species, whole plant of 8 species, roots of 7 species, branches of 6 species, wood, seeds, and shoots of 5 species each, bark of 4 species, stems and flowers of 3 species each, cones, resin, and needles of 2 species each, and bulbs of 1 species used in the preparation of remedies. Local people reported five primary methods for preparing remedies: decoction (27 species, 36%), powder (23 species, 30%), paste (13 species, 17%), infusion (5 species, 7%), and juice (8 species, 11%). In terms of administration, most medications (40 species, 73%) were taken orally, followed by topically applied medicines (4 species, 7%); 11 species (20%) were used both topically and orally. In Banjir Valley, the utilization of medicinal plants extends to the treatment of 33 different ailments by the local population. The most common uses included treatment for fever, skin issues, digestive disorders, wound healing, jaundice, urinary tract infections, lung diseases, gastrointestinal diseases, anthelmintic purposes, mouth problems, as tonics, cough, eye complaints, diabetes, toothache, analgesia (anodyne), snake bite, hemorrhoids, and scorpion sting.

INTRODUCTION

Ethnobotany is the study of interactions between people and plants (Dapar et al., 2020). Nowadays, between 70% and 95% of people in the developing world depend on plants for their primary pharmacopeia (Porrás et al., 2020). The study of ethnobotany brings together different skills and disciplines in team-based work, including botanists, anthropologists, pharmacologists, molecular biologists, and medical practitioners (Eldeen et al., 2016). Applications of ethnobotany include food, medicine, cosmetics, divination, currency, dyeing, social life and textiles, as well as

building materials, tools, money, clothing, rituals, and musical necessities. According to a WHO approximation, about 80% of the world's population depends on traditional systems of medicine for primary health care, with plants forming the dominant component among natural resources (Pandey et al., 2017). The flora of Pakistan is very rich and has unique biodiversity due to its diverse climate, soil conditions, and multiple ecological regions (Rahman et al., 2019). The four distinct seasons of Pakistan create a unique geographical setting, making it an ideal place to

carry out this important research. Of the approximately 6,000 recognized species in Pakistan, between 600 and 700 medicinal plants are thought to have therapeutic uses. About 600 species of medicinal plants have been identified and recorded in Pakistan (Asia); yet only 12% of the identified species are utilized medicinally by 60% of the population, particularly in rural areas, and about 350 medications have been developed using 456 kinds of medicinal plants to treat a variety of illnesses (Rahim et al., 2023).

Materials and Methods

Study area The Banjar Valley is a lush, green valley located on the Buner–Swat borderline. It lies at 34°35'34°35' North latitude and 72°13'72°13' East longitude. Reconnaissance surveys were carried out in Banjar Valley between 2021 and 2023. During the survey, 68 different plant species were collected for ethnobotanical study. Semi-structured questionnaires and corner meetings with informants were used to collect ethnobotanical data (Megersa and Woldetsadik, 2022). The informants were between the ages of 35 and 105 years and comprised both genders. Interviews were conducted with hakeems, nomads, and elderly residents of the area who were knowledgeable about the traditional use of plants, especially medicinal ones. Based on their traditional medical applications, collected plants were divided into various usage classes (Ishtiaq et al., 2022). The dried plant samples were mounted on standard herbarium sheets following conventional methods. Identification and recognition of plants were done following the Flora of Pakistan (Nasir and Ali, 1970–1989; Ali and Qaisar, 1993–2019). Following alphabetical order, the voucher specimens were systematically numbered and a comprehensive floristic checklist was compiled. The herbarium sheets were then submitted to the Herbarium, Department of Botany, Abdul Wali Khan University Mardan.

Results and Discussion

A total of 68 plant species were reported as medicinal in the Banjar Valley. Nearly all plant parts were utilized for remedy preparation. Leaves were the most commonly used part,

reported in 29 species, followed by fruits (16 species) and the whole plant (8 species). Other plant parts included roots (7 species), branches (6), wood, seeds, and shoots (5 each), bark (4), stems and flowers (3 each), cones, resin, and needles (2 each), and bulbs (1 species). The dominance of leaves in medicinal preparations aligns with findings from other ethnobotanical studies worldwide (Shakya, 2016; Bhatt et al., 2023), as leaves are often rich in bioactive compounds, easy to harvest, and renewable. The diversity of plant parts used demonstrates the comprehensive local knowledge of medicinal plant applications in the region. Local inhabitants reported five primary methods for preparing remedies. Decoctions were most common (27 species; 36%), followed by powders (23 species; 30%), pastes (13 species; 17%), juice (8 species; 11%), and infusions (5 species; 7%). Regarding administration, most remedies (40 species; 73%) were taken orally, while 4 species (7%) were applied topically, and 11 species (20%) were used both orally and topically. These findings are consistent with ethnobotanical literature, where decoctions and oral administration are often preferred due to ease of preparation and rapid therapeutic effects (Khan et al., 2003; Ahmad et al., 2014; Zaman et al., 2014). Medicinal plants in the Banjar Valley were used to treat 33 different ailments. The most frequently treated conditions included gastrointestinal disorders (19 species), fever (13 species), skin problems (9 species), and stomach and lung diseases, wound healing, jaundice, and urinary tract infections (8 species each). Other uses included anthelmintic and analgesic purposes (6 species each), eye complaints, cough, and tonics (6 species each), mouth problems (4 species), diabetes, sore joints, and scorpion stings (3 species each), hypertension, toothache, snakebite, and haemorrhoids (2 species each), and various ailments reported for single species such as nervous system disorders, nosebleeds, blood purification, sedative effects, memory enhancement, liver protection, flu, dandruff, headache, antimicrobial, cancer, and infertility. The wide range of therapeutic applications underscores the importance of medicinal plants in the local healthcare system. This pattern is consistent with previous studies in Buner and other regions of Pakistan (Ali et

al., 2015; Sulaiman et al., 2020; Rahman et al., 2023), confirming the continued reliance on ethnomedicinal knowledge. Apart from medicinal applications, local people used plants for multiple purposes. Fuel, medicine, and vegetables were the most common uses (9 species each), followed by edible fruits (6 species), fencing and hedging (5 species), ornamental purposes and agricultural tools (3 species each), and timber, TSR, and washing utensils (2 species each). Other specialized uses included making tethers for animals, snuff, leaf chewing, grafting, air purification via leaf smoke, soil erosion prevention, beekeeping, sticks, pot herbs, and fodder (1 species each). These findings indicate that plants are not only crucial for health but also play a significant role in the local economy and cultural practices, emphasizing the multifunctionality of the flora in rural communities (Rahim et al., 2025; Domingo et al., 2023; Julung et al., 2023).

Table 1. Traditional ethnobotanical uses of medicinal plants and their therapeutic applications

s.no.	Species	Local Name	Ethnobotanical uses and Cure of Diseases
1.	<i>Adiantum venustum</i> D. Don	Sumbal	Treatment of cough, headache, fever, muscular pains and scorpion bites, ornamental (Natural landscaping, flower arrangement and as indoor plants).
2.	<i>Pinus wallichiana</i> A. B. Jackson	Peewuch	Fuel wood, TSR (Traditional system of resource management), timber, Resinis used in paints and varnishes.
3.	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i> Sargent	Nakhtar	Used to heal many diseases, including Afflictions of the eyes, ears, throat, blood and skin, fuel wood, TSR, Diabetes and scorpion sting. Resin is exported and is used in paints and varnishes. The needles locally called “BER” are used for making ropes.
4.	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Ooga	Reduce cholesterol and blood pressure, fight infections and prevent against cancer, vegetables.
5.	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Kabal	Fodder, ornamental (recreational areas, amenity and sport uses).
6.	<i>Poa annua</i> L.	Wakha	Fodder
7.	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Bekar	Expectorant, antispasmodic, tuberculosis, chronic bronchitis, asthma, fresh wounds, inflammatory swellings neuralgia, headache, stop bleeding from the nose and anthelmintic.
8.	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Chalweray	Disorders of the urinary system, hair tonic and boils and abscesses.
9.	<i>Pistacia chinensis</i> ssp. <i>Integerrima</i> (J. L. Stewart) Rech. f.	Shany	Jaundice
10.	<i>Hedera nepalensis</i> K. Koch	Karma	Diabetes mellitus
11.	<i>Artemisia maritima</i> L.	Juakay	Anthelmintic, antiseptic, antispasmodic, carminative, cholagogue, emmenagogue, febrifuge, stimulant, stomachic, tonic and vermifuge.
12.	<i>Senecio chrysanthemoides</i> DC.	Srajabay	Wounds and piles
13.	<i>Tagetes minuta</i> L.	Hamisha	Utilized as an ornamental and for landscaping and beautification. However, in lawns, parks and agricultural areas, it occasionally seems like a weed.
14.	<i>Impatiens balsamina</i> L.	Gul-e-mehandi	Rheumatism, isthmus, diffuse discomfort, fractures, nail inflammation, scurvy, carbuncles, diarrhea, bruises and foot illnesses.
15.	<i>Berberis lycium</i> Royle	Zyarlargay	Carminative, febrifuge, used as a tonic for diabetics, piles, toothache, septic gums,

			jaundice, chronic diarrhea and eye symptoms. Ulcer Backache, Blood purifier, Abdominal pain, Fever, Urinary tract infection.
16.	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) R. Br.	Ghowajabbay	Snake bite
17.	<i>Sarcococcaligna</i> (D.Don) Muell.-Arg.	Ladanr	The flowers are used for honey bee keeping.
18.	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Bang	Cattle cold and fever, ulcer treatment, anodyne, narcotic, tonic and boils.
19.	<i>Viburnum cotinifolium</i> D. Don	Chamyarai	The fruits are edible. Branches serve as fuel wood also used as hedge plant.
20.	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	Sarmai	Laxative, Abdominal pain and Jaundice.
21.	<i>Chenopodium botrys</i> L.	Harawa	Children dysentery.
22.	<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i> L.	Prewatay	Constipation, boils and inflammation.
23.	<i>Luffa cylindrica</i> (L.) Roem	Toorai	The young fruits are eaten as vegetable and when the outer skin is removed from the ripe fruit, the remain is used as sponge. Leaves are also used along with ash for washing utensils.
24.	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Maraz bootay	Constipation and liver disorder
25.	<i>Euphorbia helioscopia</i> L.	Mandanro	Cholera, It is also fish poison. When cooked with any other pot-herb, it depresses its flavour.
26.	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Muell.	Kambela	Abdominal pain
27.	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Arhanda	Antidote for arsenic poisoning. Seed are used for cough, fever and headache.
28.	<i>Quercus dilatata</i> Royle.	Spin Banj	The wood serve as fuel wood, due to toughness it is used for making agriculture tools, Stick ploughs, also as timber wood and as a hedge plants.
29.	<i>Quercus incana</i> Roxb.	Toor banj	Shattered bones, chest pain and urinary infections—especially when urine spills drop by drop.
30.	<i>Ajuga bracteosa</i> Wall.	Boote	Hypertension, jaundice and fever.
31.	<i>Ajuga parviflora</i> Benth.	Tarkhabootei	Antimicrobial properties, anbleeding of nose it acts like an astringent. Used in Hypertension and Hepatitis.
32.	<i>Mentha longifolia</i> (L.) L.	Velanai	Vomiting, dysentery and stomach pain.
33.	<i>Mentha spicata</i> L.	Podina	Dysentery, prevent vomiting, relieve nausea, stop bleeding, act as a febrifuge and diuretic.
34.	<i>Otostegialimbata</i> (Benth.) Boiss.	Spin azghay	Mouth sores, injuries, vision problems and gum diseases.
35.	<i>Salvia lanata</i> Roxb.	Kianr	It is used as a pot-herb.
36.	<i>Salvia moocroftiana</i> Wall. ex Benth.	Khur dug	The leaves are used for washing utensils and by young girls as Henna.

37.	<i>Thymus linearis</i> Benth.	Spairky	Fever
38.	<i>Morus alba</i> L.	Speen toot	Stimulant for the digestive system and constipation relief.
39.	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers ex Hook.f. & Thomson.	Gilo	Diuretic, tonic, memory enhancer, liver protector, diseases of the eye and a high fever.
40.	<i>Morus nigra</i> L.	Tor toot	Laxative, emollient, cooling agent, throat cleaner, anthelmintic and astringent.
41.	<i>Myrsineafricana</i> L.	Marlorang	Worm expelling. Fruit is used as eating.
42.	<i>Jasminum humile</i> L.	Ramble chambel	For the treatment of ringworm and digestive issues.
43.	<i>Olea ferruginea</i> Royle	Khonoa	Toothache
44.	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Trokay	Skin irritation, jaundice, gastrointestinal issues, warts and scorpion stings.
45.	<i>Papaver somniferum</i> L.	Khash khash	Tonic, flu and fever.
46.	<i>Indigofera heterantha</i> Wall. ex Brandis	Ghouraja	Gastric disorders, diuretic, headache and chest pain. The young branches are twisted into ropes. Its serves as fuel wood. Wood ash is used for making Snuff.
47.	<i>Trifolium repens</i> L.	Shautal	Treatment of coughs, colds, fevers and leucorrhoea. A tincture of the leaves is applied as an ointment to gout, Vegetables (The fresh plants have been used for centuries as additives to salads and other meals consisting of leafy vegetables).
48.	<i>Vicia sativa</i> L.	Chilo	Vegetables
49.	<i>Bistortaamplexicaulis</i> (D. Don)	Tarva panra	Medicinal (Curing ulcer, rhematic pain, backache, gout and for eyesight).
50.	<i>Rumex dentatus</i> L.	Shulkhay	As an antiseptic for skin problems and wounds.
51.	<i>Rumex hastatus</i> D. Don	Tarookay	Regarding arthritic joints, purgative and inflammatory skin caused by urtica plant. The leaf of this plant is champing by the local People.
52.	<i>Sageretia</i> thea (Osbeck) M.C.	Mamana	Dandruff, SGPT
53.	<i>Cotoneaster nummularius</i> Fisch. &C.A.Mey	Kharawa	The stem and branches are used for making walking sticks, sticks for animal controlling, sticks for punishment etc. Agriculture appliances. It is also used for making fences.
54.	<i>Duchesnea indica</i> (Andrews) Focke in Engl. & Prantl.	Zamky toot	Cough and throatache.
55.	<i>Pyrus pashia</i> Buchanan-Hamilton ex D. Don	Tangai	Digestive disorders, fuel wood, fruit. The fruit are edible. The wood serve as fuel wood. It is commonly used for grafting of some plant. Such as <i>Pyrus malus</i> and <i>P.commun</i> is i.e. Root stock.
56.	<i>Rubus ulmifolius</i> Schott	Gouraj	The fruits are edible. It is also used as hedge plant around field. They are also used for Fencing.
57.	<i>Skimmialaureola</i> (DC.) Sieb. &Zucc. ex	Nazar panra	Generally it is believed that smoke of leaves purify air and repel evils.

	Walp		
58.	<i>Salix tetrasperma</i> Roxb.	Wala	It is planted to prevent water erosion of soil. Wood is used for making furniture. Branches serve as fuel wood.
59.	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	Ghoraskay	Healing of wounds and treatment of fungal infection.
60.	<i>Verbascum thapsus</i> L.	Gedar tambaku	Wounds healing.
61.	<i>Solanum nigrum</i> L.	Kachmachu	Diseases of the skin, enlarged, painful testicles, tongue inflammation and jaundice.
62.	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm. f.	Manraghonay	Coughs and fevers.
63.	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal	Ketelal	TB patients and diuretics.
64.	<i>Wikstroemia canescens</i> Meisn.	Ktan	Lumpy skin disease and the bark is used for making of tether for animal.
65.	<i>Ferula jaeschkeana</i> Vatke.	Sqwara	Pregnancy
66.	<i>Debregeasia salicifolia</i> (D. Don) Rendle	Ajlai	The branches are used as fuel wood and the fruits are edible.
67.	<i>Viola canescens</i> Wall. ex Roxb.	Banafsha	Wounds healing.
68.	<i>Vitis Jacquemontii</i> Parker	Ghedarkwar	The fruits are edible and gynaecological illnesses including infertility.

Fig. 1. Percentage-wise analysis of traditional herbal medicine preparation methods

Fig. 2. Percentage wise distribution of traditional routes of drug administration

Fig. 3. Percentage composition of medicinal plant use across ailment categories

Conclusion

This ethnobotanical study documents the traditional use of 68 medicinal plant species in Banjar Valley, District Buner, for the treatment of 33 different ailments. Leaves were the most commonly used plant part, while decoction and oral administration were the predominant preparation and application methods. The findings highlight the importance of medicinal plants in local healthcare and emphasize the need to preserve and scientifically validate indigenous ethnomedicinal knowledge.

REFERENCES

Ahmad, M., Sultana, S., Fazli-Hadi, S., Ben Hadda, T., Rashid, S., Zafar, M., Khan, M. A., Khan, M. P. Z., & Yaseen, G. (2014). An ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants in high mountainous region of Chail valley (District Swat–Pakistan). *Journal of Ethnobiology and Ethnomedicine*, 10, 1–18.

Ali, S. I., & Qaiser, M. (Eds.). (1993–2019). *Flora of Pakistan*, Vols. 194–222. Department of Botany, University of Karachi: Karachi.

- Ali, S., Perveen, A., & Qaiser, M. (2015). Vegetation structure, edaphology and ethnobotany of Mahaban and Malka (District Buner), KPK, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Botany*, 47, 15–22.
- Bhatt, M. D., Joshi, D. R., Bhandary, G. S., Maharjan, S., Tamang, T., Guragain, D., & Kunwar, R. M. (2023). Documentation of plant biodiversity and ethnobotany in Jhilmil area, Kanchanpur, Nepal. *Banko Janakari*, 33, 8–15.
- Dapar, M. L. G., & Alejandro, G. J. D. (2020). Ethnobotanical studies on indigenous communities in the Philippines: Current status, challenges, recommendations and future perspectives. *Journal of Complementary Medicine Research*, 11(1), 432–446.
- Domingo-Fernández, D., Gadiya, Y., Mubeen, S., Bollerman, T. J., Healy, M. D., Chanana, S., Sadovsky, R. G., Healey, D., & Colluru, V. (2023). Modern drug discovery using ethnobotany: A large-scale cross-cultural analysis of traditional medicine reveals common therapeutic uses. *iScience*.
- Eldeen, I. M., Effendy, M. A., & Tengku-Muhammad, T. S. (2016). Ethnobotany: Challenges and future perspectives. *Research Journal of Medicinal Plants*, 10(6–7), 382–387.
- Ishtiaq, M., Khanum, H., Hussain, I., Parveen, A., Maqbool, M., Thind, S., Hussain, T., Azeem, M., Shabir, F., & Elansary, H. O. (2022). Ethnobotanical inventory and medicinal perspectives of herbal flora of Shiwalik mountainous range of District Bhimber, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Pakistan. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0265028.
- Julung, H., Supiandi, M. I., Ege, B., Zubaidah, S., & Mahanal, S. (2023). Ethnobotany of medicinal plants in the Dayak Linoh tribe in Sintang district, Indonesia. *Biodiversitas Journal of Biological Diversity*, 24(2).
- Khan, A., Gilani, S. S., Hussain, F., & Durrani, M. J. (2003). Ethnobotany of Gokand Valley, District Buner, Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Biological Sciences*, 6(362), 9.
- Megersa, M., & Woldetsadik, S. (2022). Ethnobotanical study of medicinal plants used by local communities of DamotWoyde district, Wolaita zone, southern Ethiopia. *Nusantara Bioscience*, 14(1).
- Nasir, E., & Ali, S. I. (1970–1989). *Flora of Pakistan*. Nos. 1–190. National Herbarium, PARC, Islamabad and Department of Botany, University of Karachi.
- Pandey, A. K., & Tripathi, Y. C. (2017). Ethnobotany and its relevance in contemporary research. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Studies*, 5(3), 113–119.
- Porras, G., Chassagne, F., Lyles, J. T., Marquez, L., Dettweiler, M., Salam, A. M., Samarakoon, T., Shabih, S., Farrokhi, D. R., & Quave, C. L. (2020). Ethnobotany and the role of plant natural products in antibiotic drug discovery. *Chemical Reviews*, 121(6), 3495–3560.
- Rahim, F., Khalid, S., ur Rehman, M. A., Ali, A., Samad, M., & Ali, A. (2025). Ethnomedicinal evaluation of therapeutically and economically significant plants in Umarzai, District Charsadda, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. *Frontiers in Medical and Health Research*, 3(6), 889–902.
- Rahim, S., Shah, A., & Iqbal, S. (2023). Ethnobotany of medicinal plants in Surghar Range of Pakistan. *Ethnobotany Research and Applications*, 26, 1–72.
- Rahman, I. U., Afzal, A., Iqbal, Z., Ijaz, F., Ali, N., Shah, M., Ullah, S., & Bussmann, R. W. (2019). Historical perspectives of ethnobotany. *Clinics in Dermatology*, 37(4), 382–388.
- Rahman, S., Jan, G., Jan, F. G., Hashmi, S. J., & Rahim, H. U. (2023). Exploration of ethnomedicinal plants, diversity and their practices in human healthcare in Tehsil Mandan, District Buner, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*.
- Shakya, A. K. (2016). Medicinal plants: Future source of new drugs. *International Journal of Herbal Medicine*, 4(4), 59–64.

- Sharma, M., Saini, L., Kumar, P., Panigrahi, S., & Dwivedi, P. (2023). Strategies for conservation and sustainable use of medicinal plants. In *Medicinal Plants: Biodiversity, Biotechnology and Conservation* (pp. 251-263). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Sulaiman Shah, S., Khan, S., Bussmann, R. W., Ali, M., Hussain, D., & Hussain, W. (2020). Quantitative ethnobotanical study of indigenous knowledge on medicinal plants used by the tribal communities of Gokand Valley, District Buner, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. *Plants*, 9(8), 1001.
- Zaman, S., Farrukh, H., & Muhammad, I. (2014). Traditional knowledge on plant resources of Ashezai and Salarzai valleys, District Buner, Pakistan. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 8(1), 42-53.

